

“I think open access is terrific for people early on in their career.”

Senior academics often advise early career researchers to publish with a traditional press. They say publishing a book open access could harm their career prospects. But, when Winters was the editor of an early career researcher book series, she found that open access book publishing was hugely beneficial to the fledgling scholars she worked with. Their work rapidly gained a high profile, getting their names noticed in academic circles. From that, they gained lots of networking opportunities.

“The early career researchers benefitted enormously from the attention their open access books got.

And they were able to cross-promote each other's work, building a real community around that. It was really effective in career development terms.”

More established scholars also benefit from open access book publishing – they too reach a wider audience, and more quickly, increasing the likelihood of their research having an impact. And the research process and quality of output is richer and potentially stronger because academics can easily access a more diverse range of source material.

Jane Winters,
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Humanities and
Director of the Digital
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of London

Why Winters thinks publishing a book open access is good for early career researchers

It boosts research dissemination

It is good for profile building and networking

It can create a buzz around research

There are presses specifically aimed at new scholars